

THEORETICAL AND ORGANIZATIONAL BASIS OF ORGANIZING FINANCIAL CONTROL IN THE PUBLIC SECTOR

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Annotation. The purpose of this article is to reveal the main aspects and principles of financial control with scientific drawing and analysis. Today, the main goal of financial control is to objectively study the actual situation existing in the inspected object and to identify the factors that have a negative impact on the adoption and execution of management decisions. consists of detection or prevention.

Keywords. finance, control objects, budget, principles, local offices, economy, accounting chamber.

The emergence and development of financial control is closely related to the organization and development of the state financial system. Organization of financial control is considered a mandatory element of financial resource management, and such management reflects responsibility to society. Control is not the final goal, control is an integral part of the management system and a necessary condition for the effective functioning of the country's economy and financial system. Financial control is a structural element of state control over the management of socio-economic development of society. As the Honorable President Sh. Mirziyoyev stated - "Our most important priority is to further strengthen macroeconomic stability and maintain high rates of economic growth, including ensuring that the State budget is balanced at all levels, the national currency and the price level in the domestic market"¹. The state budget fulfills important socio-economic tasks by financing the needs of budget managers. Despite its importance for the development of the economy and society as a whole, the budget system of Uzbekistan has certain shortcomings related to high centralization, problems of financing the budget deficit in the context of a high level of public debt, and others. As a form of the control management cycle, it is necessary to evaluate the validity and effectiveness of the management decisions taken or adopted, to determine the level of implementation of these decisions, to determine the degree of deviation (difference) from the established parameters of actual results and normative instructions, and to make management decisions aimed at eliminating negative situations. is a system for monitoring, comparing, checking and analyzing the activity of the managed object for the purpose of acceptance.

Financial control is a specific purpose-oriented activity of the responsible bodies, which ensures that the financial transactions of operating economic entities

are carried out within the framework of established laws, analyzes their effectiveness and develops proposals for their further improvement.

The purpose of financial control is not just control, but its purpose is to take measures to correct the situation, in some cases to hold the perpetrators accountable, to collect compensation for the damage caused, or to be able to prevent or reduce such violations in the future. as much as possible, it is to prevent deviations from the standards adopted at the initial stage and violations of the law, to increase the efficiency of material resources and to determine the cost savings. The importance of financial control is that, with its help, first, to monitor compliance with the legal order by state and public organizations, enterprises, institutions, organizations, citizens in their financial activities; secondly, it is carried out by checking the economic validity and efficiency of the financial actions being carried out, and the compliance of these actions with the tasks facing the state. Thus, financial control serves as an important means of ensuring compliance with the law and appropriateness of actions during the implementation of financial activities.

In the process of transition to a market economy, the goals and tasks, types and forms of financial control have changed radically. Now, it is not only for the purpose of punishment, but also to provide advice and instructions in order to control the full collection of the funds necessary for the performance of the state's tasks and the effective spending of the budget funds. . Today, the financial control system includes the types, forms and methods of control along with the controllers and the controlled. The successful and effective conduct of financial control depends on the level of its organization and the types, forms and methods of control.

Figure 1. Types according to entities performing financial control

is carried out by state authorities (the Supreme Assembly, the Chamber of Accounts, the Ministry of Finance, the State Tax Committee, the State Customs Committee, etc.). The main purpose of this type of financial control is to ensure the interests of the state and society in terms of revenue and spending of state expenses. State financial control is a complex and purpose-oriented system of economic and legal actions of authorities and administrative bodies, based on the main laws of the state. The Constitution of the country plays a decisive role in the organization of financial control. Its legal regulation depends on the type of state, its socio-political orientation, the level of economic development, and the ratio of forms of ownership. State financial control is aimed at monitoring the value proportions of the gross domestic product distribution. This control applies to all channels of movement of monetary resources (distributed) related to the formation of state financial resources, their full and timely flow and their targeted use.

This means, first of all, the development, discussion, approval and execution of budgets and non-budgetary funds at all levels, control over the financial activities of enterprises and organizations, banks and financial corporations.

According to the place of inspection, inspections by tax and customs authorities, financial control by state and social extrabudgetary funds and other bodies are divided into camera and on-site inspection. Forms of financial control are usually classified according to the regulations of implementation, according to the time of implementation, according to subjects of control and objects of control (Fig. Inspection means checking the situation in some sections of the activity of separate control procedures, checking by comparison with the information reflected in the documents (tax, report, balance, expense) and registers. During the inspection, some violations of financial discipline, errors in accounting (financial) accounting, distortion of accounting (financial) reporting data are identified. According to the place of inspection, inspections by tax and customs authorities, financial control by state and social extrabudgetary funds and other bodies are divided into camera and on-site inspections.

is carried out by state financial control bodies in order to identify, eliminate and prevent violations of budget legislation by objects of state financial control, as well as to prevent corruption-related offenses in the budget sphere.

Financial control is carried out through special principles. Control principles are scientifically developed and practical political, organizational and legal foundations of control, their adherence ensures the effectiveness of control. The principles of control determine the general order of control in the field of finance. On the basis of many years of experience, the main principles of the organization of state financial control in the world have been produced, and every civilized country is following and striving to do so. These principles require legality, inviolability, objectivity, competence, transparency. Legitimacy is one of the important principles of financial control, first of all, it implies legality in the use of state and local financial and material resources, and secondly, the activities of control bodies should be organized within the scope of their powers established by law. Immunity - the inviolability of control bodies should be established by law. Independence is a factor that ensures the effectiveness of the work of supervisory bodies, and it assumes financial independence and independence of the supervisory body.

Objectivity and competence - implies the unconditional compliance of the current legislation by the persons conducting the control, their high professional level. The principle of transparency requires close contact of supervisory bodies with public mass media. Because control bodies directly or indirectly serve the interests of a group of people or the entire population. Control-economic work affects the

increase of production efficiency, achievement of high economic results, increase of state revenues, and efficient and appropriate use of state funds.

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